

Development and application of a teaching-learning model among eduScrum and active learning methodologies

Erik Teixeira Lopes¹, André Luiz Aquere¹

¹ University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil.

Email: erik.lopes05@gmail.com, andre@unb.br

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5095336>

Abstract

The present work addresses the structuring and application of a teaching-learning model, which explores the interface between eduScrum and active learning methodologies, in particular Project-Based Learning and the Flipped Classroom, in teaching-learning management of projects. Both eduScrum and active learning methodologies bring key concepts such as regular feedbacks, prioritization of content applicable in practice and centralization of the process in the student. Thus, a framework of 5 sprints was structured with 6 classes each to use both approaches in a complementary way, detailing step by step during the research. The application was carried out in the discipline Project Management and Multidisciplinary Teams in the semester of 2020/1, offered by the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering at the University of Brasília. The steps involved in the project were: literature review; application of a questionnaire to identify the requirements of the discipline in the students' view; structuring the model and the necessary adaptations for remote education, depending on the pandemic caused by the Coronavirus; application and evaluation of the developed model. The implementation of the model throughout the semester was highlighted by the positive reception by the students and the relevance of the projects developed by the groups and allowed to identify opportunities for improvement in the dynamics of the activities, in the schedule and in the evaluation method. In the end, an anonymous questionnaire was obtained with the students who took the course a Net Promoter Score of 82 points and an average satisfaction of 4.5 on a scale of 1 to 5. These results points to the potential of using this method of non-traditional teaching in engineering education.

Keywords: EduScrum, Project Management, Project Based Learning, Flipped classroom.

1 Introduction

Worldwide spreading from the book "The art of doing double in half the time", by Jeff Sutherland (2014), Scrum is a methodology that, although initially created for the development of software, gained space for its application in several industries and services, including education. In this sense, eduScrum (Delhji et al, 2016) is an alternative to the traditional teaching / learning model, focusing on iterative, transparent, and agile learning, with successful experiences in different educational contexts.

At the same time, in recent years there has been a growth on the part of higher education institutions in the application of new concepts and learning methods in engineering education. It is a demand from the market and from the students themselves, by more dynamic, applied, and participatory classes, to acquire the skills and competencies necessary for the profession. Thus, Active Learning has become the focus of discussions around the world (Filho et al, 2019).

In this sense, the present work aims to use the synergy and similarities between eduScrum and active learning methodologies to optimize the results of teaching in engineering, through learning cycles and direct interaction with students. Thus, a model was developed and applied involving both eduScrum and active learning methodologies in the semester 2020/1 in the discipline Project Management and Multidisciplinary Teams, at the University of Brasília.

2 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical basis for structuring the interface that was applied in the discipline was based on three topics: scrum / eduScrum, Flipped Classroom and Project-Based Learning.

2.1 Scrum / eduScrum

Scrum is a project management methodology popularized since 2014. Among its characteristics, flexibility stands out, which works by defining an incremental process that can be applied in processes and projects of different sizes, using adaptability to ensure constant evolution. In his book, Sutherland (2014) presents three pillars that support Scrum: transparency, inspection, and adaptability. The application of these allows the user to deliver creative solutions based on the constant adaptability and learning process, with the importance of each pillar reflected in the team's roles, artifacts and events that characterize the methodology.

In the educational context, Scrum has been adapted for application in teaching, with experiences at different levels of education and countries. According to Delhij et al (2016) eduScrum is a light model, easy to understand and difficult to apply, in which students can solve problems to achieve learning goals and objectives, based on autonomy, teamwork and transparency, guiding the student with a focus on "what to do", not "how to do". The eduScrum team is formed by the teacher (product owner), students and the Scrum master (role played by a student). The main events foreseen in the application of the model permeate the sprints or learning cycles, namely the planning meeting, the stand-up, the review, and the sprint retrospective (Delhji et al, 2016).

2.2 Flipped Classroom

The Flipped classroom is an active learning model used at different educational levels, which gained notoriety from the publication of the book *Flip your classroom: reach every student in every class every day* (Bergmann and Sams, 2012). In general, the Flipped classroom consists of a methodology in which students prepare the theoretical content prior to the class and develop activities such as exercises, which are normally homework tasks in the traditional model (Filho et al, 2019). Your process can be classified into three stages: pre-class, class, and post-class.

In the pre-class, the teacher guides and provides materials so that students can have a first contact with the topic to be addressed, so that the student lists doubts and questions. During the class, the teacher must then stimulate activities to condense and clarify the content, such as synthesizing, analysing and debating, using different strategies for optimizing learning. The content base previously obtained by the students allows the teacher to provide a moment of real learning in the classroom, in addition to the development of other student skills in parallel with the technical content of the discipline, such as teamwork, argumentation and oratory. The evaluation process can also occur, naturally, at the time of the class or not, using different strategies such as seminars, assignments, or quick tests. Finally, the post-class consists of the student revising and extrapolating the content, for example with applications in his daily life and in other areas of knowledge (Filho et al, 2019).

2.3 Project-Based Learning

There is a wide variety of research that addresses the Project-Based Learning (PBL), due to the different definitions found and the lack of universal acceptance (Thomas, 2000), so that there are also several models for its application. In short, Project-Based Learning is an active learning methodology based on real everyday situations (Pereira, Barreto and Pazeti, 2017) (Bell, 2010) (Thomas, 2000). This proposal seeks to bring not only technical knowledge, but also skills such as problem solving, investigation and decision making, based on the guidance of a teacher (Thomas, 2000).

Five aspects define the PBL: the resolution of the problem can be proposed by the students themselves; the initiative to solve the problem comes from the students and requires integration between educational activities; a final product is delivered, consistent with the initial problem; the solution to the problem is usually developed as a project; the teacher does not exercise an authoritarian role, but as a consultant to the teams that will develop the project (Pereira, Barreto and Pazeti, 2017).

3 Methodology

This is an Action Research carried out in the discipline of project management and multidisciplinary teams during the semester of 2020.1. We opted for this methodology because it converged the opinions of a teacher advisor and the research student who experiences the educational experience. Still, according to Tripp (2005),

Action Research presents activities in both the practical and research areas, in addition to being innovative, participatory, interventionist, problematizing, documented and deliberate, some of the characteristics that differentiate it from other investigative research, such as routine practice and scientific research.

To this end, the work was organized in four main stages: exploration of the project's theme, in order to raise the main aspects to be addressed and to support the discussions and solutions presented; review of the existing course, based on the literature and on the demands discussed with the guiding professor for teaching project management; application of the proposed model of learning in a course of the Civil Engineering at the University of Brasilia in the second semester of 2020; analysis of the results obtained, in addition to the necessary adjustments according to the progress of the discipline's application.

The exploration of the project's theme consisted of an exploratory research, supporting the discussions and solutions through books, articles, and other related works. The main topics to be addressed, according to a previous survey, were eduScrum, learning methodologies and project management.

The review of the existing course consisted of elaborating and formalizing a model that used the lessons of the bibliographic review to meet the demands identified with the students. In this sense, an online questionnaire was carried out to collect the requirements with the students. Based on this understanding, the learning methodologies to be adopted and the structured interface between eduScrum and the activities provided for in the course plan were chosen, in addition to the identification of the recommended bibliographies and the structure of the project to be developed in groups by the students. This stage ended with the elaboration of the course's plan.

The application of the reformulated discipline occurred in the first half of 2020, remotely, due to the world pandemic and the interruption of face-to-face activities by the University of Brasilia. Initially, an expectations questionnaire was collected from the class participants and, at the end of the semester, again, to compare the results. During the activities, the teacher acted directly, leading the class, while the other researcher was a student of the class, taking part in the activities as a member of one of the groups. In addition, a diary of the perceptions of both was made during the course, which was reviewed and discussed at the end of each sprint, in order to propose improvements even during the course of the school semester.

Finally, at the end of the class period, the analysis and consolidation of the data obtained was carried out, evaluating the satisfaction and results of the students who attended Project Management and Multidisciplinary Teams.

4 Model development

4.1 Requirements gathering and identification of the existing interface

Prior to the beginning of the enrolment period at the University of Brasilia, already having the initial hypotheses of the model to be proposed for the discipline of Project Management and Multidisciplinary Teams, the requirements were surveyed with the students of the department through a virtual questionnaire disseminated on social media.

The questionnaire was structured in some sections, being quick to complete in order to obtain a greater number of responses. The first section tried to characterize the sample, identifying the course, semester, gender, and age of the research participants. Then, questions were asked related to access, both in terms of infrastructure for remote classes, as well as the availability of time to take the course. In addition, questions were structured in relation to the students' previous experience with active learning methodologies and the investment they expected to make when taking an optional subject, in the case of extra-class time.

Finally, statements were structured to be evaluated by students according to the Likert scale, related to the initial hypotheses, in order to understand the value perceived by the participants in active methodologies, project management and behavioural skills, themes to be addressed in the discipline.

In total, 68 responses to the questionnaire were obtained, predominantly by the Civil Engineering and Environmental Engineering courses. The main answers that guided the research were the time of dedication expected by the students and the main aspects that add value in a discipline, being these with their respective scores on a scale of 1 to 5: multidisciplinary (4.50), addressing team management (4.53), addressing real situations (4.79), addressing project management as a whole (4.57) and develop complementary skills (4,51).

Parallel to the application of the questionnaire, the researchers worked on identifying the interface between eduScrum and active learning methodologies, mainly Project-Based Learning and the Flipped Classroom, which were selected for application in the first restructured version of the course. The objective was to identify the similarities of the proposals, in order to allow their optimization during the semester. Figure 1 illustrates the main considerations made.

Figure 1. Interface between active methodologies and eduScrum.

4.2 Structuring of the Discipline Proposal

Initially, it was decided to maintain the discipline with 4 class hours per week, divided into two classes, for a total of 15 weeks of the academic semester, a model that had already been applied in other semesters. Based on this planning, a preliminary schedule and work plan was prepared. In addition, the class was limited to a number of 20 students.

Then, the weeks were divided into sprints, in order to guarantee the characteristics of eduScrum and the educational objectives. All planning was carried out previously, but later validated, in the first sprint, together with the students. In this sense, we opted for a collaborative process, so that the first sprint mainly addressed the alignment of expectations and objectives, allowing the prior planning to be adapted according to the class that is taking the discipline in the semester in question, as long as it meets the needs of the students' minimum requirements foreseen by the teacher.

The discipline was then divided into 5 sprints of equal duration, to facilitate the control for a first experience and to establish a modular and replicable structure for courses of greater or lesser duration. It is important that each of these sprints has the minimum events planned (planning, division of tasks, stand up, sprint review and retrospective) and a clear objective.

a) Sprint I (introduction): the first cycle of the course is focused on receiving students and adapting to the methodology, in addition to aligning expectations and work agreements. The idea is to address some initial project management concepts to contextualize students, but also to present the Scrum approach, as it will be necessary for the development of the course. The planned deliveries are the course plan, adjusted according to the agreement between students and teacher, and the project contract, with the rules of coexistence, deadlines and other agreements signed by the group.

b) Sprints II to IV (development): the development cycles consist of the main technical aspect of the course, in fact addressing the contents foreseen for the discipline and structuring the learning with the active methodologies. The order of presentation follows the logic of a project, using the conventional flow (beginning, planning, execution, monitoring and closing), with some topics in advance to facilitate coexistence and group work, such as communication management. The planned deliveries are related to the content covered in the classroom, applied to the discipline project. Thus, there is a parallel between theory and practice and knowledge is solidified within smaller cycles and close to the students' reality.

c) Sprint V (closure): the last cycle aims at evaluating and closing the discipline, in addition to addressing some additional content, such as project management references. Both its delivery and its development are based on the closure of the discipline project and the presentation, to formalize the conclusion of the "contract" established in the first sprint. It is important to emphasize that this cycle addresses not only the assessment of the teacher to the students, but also the self-assessment of each one and the retrospective of the entire project, in this case, of the school semester.

Figure 2 consolidates in a simplified way the structure adopted for the course.

Figure 2. Basic structure adopted for the course.

Understanding the sprints in a macro way, the detailed approach for the 3-week cycles is presented. As already mentioned, the idea of being fixed-size cycles facilitates both the organization, as well as the planning and execution of sprints, adopting a simpler structure that is repeated during the development of the semester. In total, there are 6 classes of approximately 2 hours in duration:

- a) Lesson 1: the first class of each sprint presents the objective of that cycle, proposes goals and deliverables, and allows students to plan. It also begins to address the concepts that will be developed;
- b) Lessons 2, 3 and 4: these 3 classes are the technical development of the project management content, aiming to bring the robustness and the concepts necessary both for the development of the project and for its day-to-day application;
- c) Lesson 5: this is a planned class that has two main functions in the schedule: bringing an applied and complementary approach to project management, whether with the application of workshops or cases based on real situations or discussion of complementary skills for a project manager, as oratory and organization; or

allow a break in the schedule, so that in the event of unforeseen events or holidays the main contents and events are not compressed, and this class may function as a replacement for some of the others;

d) Lesson 6: the sprint closing class, aims to recap and reinforce the main points covered, in addition to allowing the assessment of the cycle, either formally (punctuated activities) or informally (individual student discussion and reflection).

4.3 Necessary adaptations

After the enrolment period and given the context of remote classes adopted by the University of Brasilia, some adaptations in relation to the initial model were necessary. The main adaptation was the use of Microsoft Teams, made available by the institution for teachers and students, in the realization of synchronous classes. In addition, in relation to active learning methodologies, the initial proposal brought several options and uses, alternating between various methodologies. Since the objective of the course is not to explain active methodologies, but project management, it was realized that it would be very complex to switch between so many methods, decreasing productivity and losing the focus of the course. Thus, the Flipped classroom and project-based learning were selected exclusively as methodologies to be adopted this semester.

The Flipped Classroom was chosen because it is closer to the students' reality and feasible in classes with more than 15 students, as was the case. In addition, its remote realization is not impaired, so it was considered easier to perform than other options. Project-Based Learning, on the other hand, was adopted because in addition to being an active methodology, it allows the use of concepts learned in the discipline itself, of project management, and was one of the most relevant points when adding value in a discipline, according to the questionnaire presented previously. In addition, both methodologies were already used by the teacher responsible for the discipline.

Finally, other relevant changes in relation to the initial proposal were the format of the classes with external guests and the contents and ordering of some themes. In relation to classes with guests, due to being remote, more expository seminars were given, with themes related to project management, while in the initial proposal, workshops and softs skills courses were also foreseen. The themes, however, were reorganized in order to prioritize interpersonal relationships and organization, considered essential for students in such an atypical semester, facilitating their development and application from the beginning of semester.

5 Results

At the end of the course, an anonymous, self-administered, quantitative and qualitative questionnaire was applied to all students enrolled in the academic semester. Regarding the general degree of satisfaction of the discipline, all students scored grades 4 or 5, on a scale of 1 to 5, so that the general average was 4.47.

In addition, students also rated a scale from 1 to 5, the importance of some aspects of the discipline, such as the use of foreign literature, active methodologies, and seminars with external guests. Only "Use of foreign literature" received "indifferent" grades on the scale, while all other items were classified as "important" or "very important" by the students. It is worth mentioning the use of active learning methodologies, which obtained the highest number of grades "very important" among the evaluations, which shows a great acceptance of students in the proposed approach, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Answer about importance for the course.

Another point analysed were operational aspects of the discipline, such as the format of the classes, the scope of the project and evaluation methods. In this sense, the content covered, the discipline project, the evaluation methods and the bibliography used received the best evaluations. The format of the classes received some "Indifferent" notes, and the students commented that remote teaching has somewhat impaired communication and interaction at times, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Answers about average satisfaction.

Finally, students were asked to answer the question "On a scale of 0 to 10, what would be the chance for you to recommend the GEPEM course to another person?", used to calculate the Net Promoter Score (NPS), as established by Frederick Reichheld, director of Bain and Company (Reichheld, 2003). After the calculation, the NPS obtained was 82. According to Bain and Company itself, this is already a note of the so-called zone of excellence, which indicates that the product or service is very well evaluated by customers and actively disseminated by them.

6 Final Considerations

In view of the developments, the interface between active learning methodologies and an agile project management method applied to education was satisfactory. The proposed model was applied within a limited context but managed to be validated and criticized in order to be better understood. It is noted that the satisfaction rate obtained by students with the discipline of Project Management and Multidisciplinary Teams was high, exceeding initial expectations. In addition, some key concepts proposed, such as active methodologies, the presence of external guests and the elaboration of real projects were extremely well received and approved by the students, with the main aspects being positively evaluated.

In relation to active methodologies, project-based learning proved to be efficient as an engagement factor and an excellent assessment tool, making deliveries clearer and allowing a direct application of the studied project management concepts. It is also believed that because it does not involve financial profits and the obligation to contribute to the University of Brasília, prerequisites defined by the professor in the elaboration of the projects, the dedication of the students with the result was greater.

However, during the process of applying and analysing the results of the method, points for improvement were identified. The biggest challenge encountered is to define structures, artifacts and tools that allow eduScrum events to be carried out within a shorter period of time and with a larger number of people, in order not to mischaracterize the method. Another point of attention is the definition of a schedule with time off, so that situations that may result in the cancellation of classes do not affect the deadlines globally. In addition, it is necessary to clearly define the evaluation methods and align them with the students, to obtain greater transparency in the process, one of the defining characteristics of Scrum. Finally, if the remote education scenario continues in the next semesters, it is interesting to evaluate the use of other collaborative platforms, in order to integrate less participatory students and bring greater homogeneity in the class.

Even so, the present pilot experience shows itself as a promising alternative for increasing student engagement and the use of active methodologies, in contrast to the predominant expository curriculum existing in engineering in general, possibly being applicable in other disciplines, both on-site and remote. It is expected, in the continuation of this line of research, to improve the proposed model and apply it to other contexts for greater validation.

7 References

- Bell, S. (2010) Project-Based Learning for the 21st Century: skills for the Future. *The clearing house*, 83:2,39-43, 2010.
- Bergmann, J.; Sams, A. Flip your classroom: reach every student in every class every day. International Society for Technology in Education, 2012.
- Delhij, A., Solingen, R. V., & Wijnands, W. (2016). O Guia eduScrum [eduScrum guide]. Time eduScrum.
- Filho, G. E., Sauer, L. Z., Almeida, N., N., & Villas-Boas, V. (2019). Uma nova sala de aula é possível [A new classroom is possible]. LTC.
- Pereira, M. A. C.; Barreto, M. A. M.; Pazeti, M. (2017) Application of Project-Based Learning in the first year of an Industrial Engineering Program: lessons learned and challenges. *Production*, 27 (spe), 2017.
- Project Management Institute (PMI). (2017). A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK Guide). Newton Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- Reichheld, F. F. (2003) The One Number You Need to Grow. *Harvard Business Review*. Disponível em <https://hbr.org/2003/12/the-one-number-you-need-to-grow>
- Sutherland, J. (2014). Scrum: The art of doing twice the work in half the time. LeYa.
- Thomas, J. W. (2000) A review of research on Project-Based learning. The Autodeks Foundation, San Rafael, California, 2000.
- Tripp, D. (2005) Pesquisa-ação: uma introdução metodológica [Action Research: a methodology introduction]. *Educação e Pesquisa*, São Paulo, v. 31, n. 3, p. 443-466, set./dez. 2005.